

Torsion as a design driver in plate-bending-active tensile structures

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Abstract

This paper investigates and demonstrates the structural and architectural potentials of torsion in plate elements for bending-active tensile structures and evaluates the limits to which torsion can be employed in plate-hybrid structures. Bending-active tensile structures are a novel typology of lightweight structures utilizing integrated bending-active elements as support for a membrane structure. However, aspects of scalability, use of bending-active plates, a membrane-integrated construction process and multiple states of equilibrium are current difficulties found in designing these structures and are mostly unexplored research fields. This new research investigates the advantages of plate structures in conjunction with the geometric stiffening and prestressing effect of tensile elements, the control of geometry, and bi-stable equilibrium state of the membrane through the introduction of torsion during construction. By incorporating an assembly-based approach, the relationship between the bending-active and membrane elements is analyzed and extrapolated to determine the requirements for further prototypical development. The research is conducted by means of small-scale case studies and an integrated finite element analysis. By analyzing the reciprocal interdependence of structural design, assembly processes, material design and architectural geometry, a novel approach to the realization of form- and bending-active structures is proposed.

Keywords: Bending-active, membrane structures, form-finding, structural system, torsion

1. Introduction

Bending-active tensile (BAT) structures introduce a recently new integrative solution into the field of lightweight architecture. This combination of bending-active elements with a tensile element generates challenges for designers due to the complexity in the necessary integrated form-finding and analysis simulations combined with the reciprocal equilibrium, as well as the high level of detail required in fabrication and erection of these form-active structures. These BAT structures remain a challenge, but current developments in CAD and CAE allow designers to engage in that complexity and generate new architectural and structural possibilities in simulating and generating geometry (Van Mele et al. [17], Nembrini [12], Holden Deleuran et al. [6], Suzuki and Knippers [16]).

Elastically bent structures have a long history in vernacular architecture and the use of circular and plate cross-sections is little more than conventional (Lienhard et al. [10]). To the knowledge of the authors, current built BAT structures only make use of circular sections (Lienhard and Knippers [11], Alpermann and Gengnagel [3], Ahlquist and Menges [1], De Laet et al. [5], and Holden Deleuran et al. [6]). Attaching a membrane structure to a circular cross-section is far less intricate and time-consuming as pockets or sleeves in the membrane perform generally very well for connecting an edge of a membrane to a support system. Additionally there is a reduction in simulation complexity for fully-symmetric sections. However, the design and the development of hybrid structures remains

mainly on an educational or academic level. Due to the limited knowledge and experience among architects and engineers, along with the challenge of understanding material behavior, element interactions with appropriate calculation tools, and complicated construction and fabrication processes, not many examples have been built. Lienhard [9] examined the geometric stiffening effect in bending-active non-warping-free cross-sections under vertical deformation through the addition of torsion. He concluded that for large rotations of rectangular cross-sections the elongation of the outer fibers leads to a dominant tensile stress in the overall section and therefore increased stiffness against external loading. However, the research is only conducted for one example, i.e. a torsional arc.

In this paper, the use of plate cross-sections in BAT structures is proposed, including the geometric stiffening and control of the plates through torsion and the prestressing of the tensile element with an integrated bi-stable equilibrium of the membrane during construction. Through the integration of simulation, analysis and investigation into the assembly approach, these plate hybrid-structures present the opportunity for an intelligent employment of material, as well as a challenge for large-scale fabrication, construction and architectural development.

2. Torsion in plate elements

In this section the work of Lienhard [9] is taken as a basis for deeper analysis. Previous research conducted by Slabbinck [14] has stated that out-of-plane bending equals torsion in large deformed bending-active structures. By applying a force that is not in the bending plane, i.e. the oscillation plane of pure bending, torsion is introduced (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Out-of-plane bending due to torsion in large deformed BAT structures

Twisting a circular cross-section compared to a plate section results in a fundamental geometric difference. The plate section enables the generation of a spatial arrangement around the longitudinal axis that can't be achieved with the same deformation in circular sections, i.e. the circular section appears the same both with and without torsion, whilst a plate section may be seen to vary in orientation. When torsion is introduced in plates and other non-fully-symmetrical cross-sections, the assumption of a planar cross-section is no longer valid since non-uniform strain occurs. Twisting and warping occurs, which is described as non-uniform torsion. In a non-warping free cross-section the warping torsion is constrained, which causes tension and compression stresses in the cross-section (Lienhard [9]). The increase of tension forces in the outer fibers of the material generates a geometric stiffening effect. This is validated in a physical and digital set-up by measuring the deflection from a vertically imposed load and by comparing the normal stresses in the plate. Digital experiments with the use of finite element analysis were conducted without bending-active behavior, i.e. without initial bending stresses. In previous research it is shown that SOFiSTiK (SOFiSTiK AG [15]) has valuable

results for the modelling of shell structures in geometrical non-linear analysis with large deformations (Slabbinck [14], and Lienhard [9]). A complex non-linear large-deformation analysis process was scripted in SOFiSTiK and allowed an easy parametrization of the input geometry, this is exported to Grasshopper (Grasshopper [8]) for post-processing and visualization in Rhinoceros 3D (Rhinoceros [13]) model space showing the deflected geometry.

Several tests were conducted (Figure 2) and their results show the decreased deflection under vertical loading (Figure 3) while twisting and the tensile stresses at the outer fibers of the cross-section are increased (Figure 4). However, when the structure starts bending out-of-plane, due to the applied torsion, the resistance to a vertical load greatly decreases as the structure is effectively in a post-buckling mode and subjected to P-Delta effects. This effect can be counteracted by constraining the geometry to its initial bending plane in a second step while maintaining the same amount of twisting in the plate. In this constrained arrangement the deflection under vertical loading is again reduced through the beneficial effect of torsional geometric stiffening (Figure 4).

Figure 2: (A) Front view physical tests on a small scale (length strip = 40cm) and increasing incrementally torsion in the strip; (B) under uniformly distributed load; (C) side view physical tests; and (D) front and top view of digital tests of larger scale models (length plate = 3m) with FEA, with /without deflection under vertical load

Figure 3: Physical and digital test results: (A) results physical testing for a 2cm width strip; (B) results physical testing for a 3cm width strip with $l=40\text{cm}$, and $t=0,6\text{mm}$; (C) results digital testing for a 20cm width plate with: $t=3\text{mm}$, $l=3\text{m}$, $E_p=4000\text{N/mm}^2$, $E_n=3000\text{N/mm}^2$, and $F=0,1\text{kN}$; and (D) normal stresses of the digital testing results in (C)

Figure 4: Digital results counteracting out-of-plane bending by constraining the geometry to its initial bending plane: (A) top view geometry; and (B) side view geometry including normal stresses in the plate

This second step, to counteract the translational displacement due to out-of-plane bending, can be provided by a prestressed membrane. When taking the assembly sequence into account, this two-step process could be reversed and membrane addition would become the primary step, while the secondary step counteracts the lateral force of the membrane with out-of-plane bending of the plate through torsion in the opposite direction (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Side view of two two-step assembly sequences

However, digital test results, including plate cross-section optimization ($t=1-4\text{mm}$, $l=3\text{m}$, $w = 20\text{cm}$, $E_p=4000\text{N/mm}^2$, $E_n=3000\text{N/mm}^2$), have shown that the required amount of prestress for membrane structures cannot be achieved purely through the torsion of plate sections with a constant width. Variable size optimization of the plate's cross-section over the bending element length might yield different results.

Next to having the geometrical stiffening effect of using plates over circular sections in BAT structures is the obvious benefit of a different area moment of inertia in the two main directions. The weak axis is ideal for elastic bending, while the strong axis can be used to withstand lateral forces. Additionally, geometrical control is added through the spatial arrangement around the longitudinal axis after twisting. This spatial arrangement adds a rotational degree of freedom to the translational degrees so that geometrically the structure can be more detailed controlled (Figure 6). This can be extended with the other two rotational axes, y and z , although they are less useful. The possibility to influence both translation and rotation opens a wide range of possibilities: e.g. the geometry can be changed after erection, or be optimized according to the curvature vector of the membrane so that the membrane force vector coincides with the strong axis of the plate. Furthermore, there is the possibility to bundle the plates to take into consideration non-linear scaling of the structural elements. When the scale of the structure increases, the thickness of the cross-section also increases as there has to be a certain rigidity in the elements. By increasing the thickness, in case of a circular cross-section, the necessary force to bend or twist the elements increases further than manual labor could accommodate for. On the one hand, bundling of circular cross-sections is paired with doubling the rods in bi-axial direction to gain rigidity in lateral direction as well, this reduces the slender appearance of these elements. On the other hand, bundling of plates allows each element to stay relatively thin but still ensures the global load bearing capacity of the system. In addition, this bundling also offers design

potential. Using the width of the plates goes beyond a mere supporting element for the membrane and becomes a part of a distinct structural and architectural appearance.

Figure 6: Torsion and bending in circular and plate cross-section

3. Assembly approach

On a fundamental level the structural system contains a tensile part and a bending-active part. With different materials and fabrication techniques it is possible to respond to specific demands for the membrane. . On the one hand, there are high strain fabrics, e.g. knitted polyester yarn, woven fabrics where the material needs to compensate the strain, etc.; on the other hand, there are low strain fabrics, e.g. PU-coated polyester, PTFE-coated fiberglass, etc. The high strain fabrics are mainly used for architectural articulations and mostly employed indoors, due to their little structural capability. The shape of the high strain membrane fits in different geometrical configurations, while the low strain fabrics require a precise cutting pattern due to their very low geometric adaption when tension is applied. The main benefit from low strain fabrics is their ability to take high forces and to stabilize the global configuration, specifically in BAT structures.

The assembly process is partially based on the use of the specific material for the membrane. Current built structures show two main connection details between bending-active elements and the membrane: (i) pockets or sleeves, and (ii) roped edges (Figure 7). The pocket or sleeve is a primary connection, i.e. the membrane is connected to the bending-active elements in a first step when the elements are still in their initial straight and flat state. This connection makes sure that the membrane and the bending-active element are connected over their whole length, which allows for an even stress distribution. In comparison, the roped edge is usually a secondary connection, i.e. the membrane is attached to a temporarily fixed, bent bending-active system.

These connections have an influence on how the membrane is prestressed. Since the prestress of the membrane is bi-axial it can differ in magnitude for every direction. Bi-axial prestress in high strain fabrics constitutes no problem, while they are far more difficult for low strain fabrics. Both connection details pose a challenge for introducing prestress in low strain fabrics according to their primary or secondary assembly process step.

Figure 7: Pocket and roped edge connection between membrane and bending-active element

Precedent examples among the few built structures are cited: Lienhard and Knippers [11] proposes, for the Marrakech Umbrella, a special device at the end of the bending-elements for introducing tangential prestress after erection as the friction between the pocket and the curved bending element is too high for slippage to occur during erection due to the high stresses in the membrane (Figure 8a). This device together with spraying silicon inside the pockets reduces the friction and ease the set-up of the prestressed hybrid. Ahlquist et al. [2] proposes a different approach for the Textile Hybrid M1 and

combines a low-strain fabric with a roped edge connection (Figure 8b). This approach might be more convenient but still poses the problem that the lacing has to be done manually and thus the prestress is achieved by pulling, which is again limited to the strength of manual labor.

Figure 8: (A) Marrakech Umbrella by Lienhard [9]; and (B) Textile Hybrid M1 by Ahlquist et al. [2]

The use of pockets with plate elements is only a valid solution as long as the plate is planar or in a pure bending position. From the moment the plates start twisting around their axis resulting in spatial bending, the use of pockets is no longer possible due to the associated friction between the tensioned membrane and the curved bending elements. The use of the roped edge and the related secondary connection process on the other hand is a more suited process. The roped edge detail can be replaced by a sewing detail (Bechert et al. [4]) and the process can be extended to an easy-assembly approach taken into consideration the non-fully symmetrical cross-section and avoid friction. The eccentricity of the detail can be advantages for the geometry and structural performance.

At the moment the most promising assembly process for plate-hybrids consists out of initially flat elements that are bent in space and temporarily fixed so they keep their geometry and position; in a second step the membrane is added and the structure find its equilibrium. In this process the second step also introduces the prestress in the membrane. However, without any other geometric deformations, the prestressing would pose challenges to the assembly process and could again only be achieved through manual labor. Instead, the biaxial prestress is added in a third step by introducing another large geometrical deformation as a post-erection tensioning, proposing a novel approach to the realization of form- and bending-active structures.

4. Integration

Following from the discussions above, the most advantageous aspects of plate structures with torsion are taken forward for further development of a conceptual system with consideration of standard requirements for connection details, membranes (no wrinkles or ponding, reasonable prestress, double curvature), material and assembly process. The analysis from the previous chapters led to the development of two conceptual systems that were later validated for the realization of form- and bending-active structures.

The first system is constructed with two bending-active plates and makes use of a basis tensile shape, the hyperboloid, which requires only two high and two low points. The membrane is added in a secondary step to the self-supporting bending-active structure and finds its reciprocal equilibrium (Figure 9a-b). The advantage of the self-supporting structure is that no temporary supports are needed, thus no external loads are imposed and all forces are resolved internally. Additionally, the torsion in the self-supporting structure not only generates geometric stiffening but also a spatial geometric configuration that allows a stable membrane-attachment without large deformations of the global structure. The width of the plates add to the global stability of the structure to resist lateral forces so that the membrane can be easily attached in an unstressed state. The third step, which was developed as a conclusion from the previous chapter, is achieved by pulling the free ends to the ground. By using the

bi-stable equilibrium state of the hyper an easy and stable construction process is enabled. This large geometrical movement prestresses the membrane bi-axially and let it find the pre-calculated equilibrium state, this movement is possible through the direction of the curvature in the twisted bending-active elements (Figure 9c). Finite element simulation results show a more distributed stress in the plates when the ends of the structure are pulled down, and less deformation at the roots of the structure. Next to the digital simulations, physical models were built to evaluate the influence of certain parameters: (i) the amount of torsion in the system, (ii) the start and end support condition of the plates, (iii) the distance between supports, and (iv) the scale of the structure, i.e. structure using 3m long plates.

Figure 9: (A) Bending-active plates in a self-supporting configuration; (B) bending-active plates with the membrane attached; and (C) prestressing the membrane by pulling the free ends of the plates down

The second system focuses on a local-level involvement of the membrane and is meant to work as an array. In a global configuration it can be used as a performative skin that can have a different degree of perforation. The system is constructed with two strand braided bending-active plates (Hudert and Weinand [7]) that are connected at both ends (Figure 10a). The assembly sequence and approach are the same as in the first system, but the third step is executed by pushing the ends towards each other so that the gap between the two strips opens up and uniaxially prestresses the membrane (Figure 10b-c). As the membrane structure is only present on a micro-scale, the degree of synclastic curvature is less important.

Figure 10: (A) Bending-active plates in a self-supporting configuration; (B) bending-active plates with the membrane attached; and (C) prestressing the membrane by pushing the free ends of the plates towards each other

Iterations of both conceptual systems can be made to show a first exploration of a theoretical idea (Figure 11). To transfer this conceptual idea to a large scale demonstrator, a number of unexplored fields should be considered, e.g. the construction detail between membrane and plate, global structural analysis including Eurocode load cases, geometrical optimization, and more.

Figure 11: Iteration of conceptual system

5. Outlook and conclusion

Until the present, very little research has been conducted concerning the presence and effect of torsion in plate-hybrid structures. The advantage of plates and torsion in these complex reciprocal structures and consequentially their structural and architectural impact was the goal of the research that is documented by this paper.

The research explores the limits and opportunities of torsion and plate elements on different levels; i.e. architecturally, structurally, geometrically, and on a construction level. The proposed conceptual systems illustrate these potentials of using plates in BAT structures that go beyond the pure structural support as the elements become part of the architectural quality and appearance.

The presented work serves as a design guide for the concept-development of BAT structures using torsion and plate cross-sections. It finds the limits to which torsion can be employed to prestress membranes. It defines the influences on different levels together with the advantages and disadvantages of using plates instead of circular cross-sections. It also opens up many continuative questions that go beyond the scope of this research, e.g. static analysis with load cases on the proposed systems, a broader exploration on the geometrical stiffening effect in plate elements including variable cross-sections, the introduced prestress by the large geometrical change on a larger scale, etc. However, the results from the preliminary presented research exhibit a promising structural and architectural performance and extend the field of lightweight architecture through an integrative design approach.

Figure 12: Physical scale model of first system with bi-stable equilibrium state of the membrane

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